

**Topic: The Progression of Homosexuality in
India**

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THE PROGRESSION OF HOMOSEXUALITY IN INDIA

According to Oxford English Dictionary, homosexuality is defined as “a pattern of sexuality where sexual and romantic thinking and behavior are directed towards people of the same sex.” Homosexuality has existed in the Indian society as early as the 4th Century AD, in texts like the Kamasutra, especially in the chapter ‘Purushayita’ refers to as men attracted to the same gender as Tritiya-Prakriti or "third nature".

Introduction

India is known for its culture, customs and traditions and homosexuality has been prevalent in our society and still continues. Majority of the societies including the Indian society, accepts Heterosexuality and deem it ‘natural’ while homosexuality is deemed as ‘unnatural’ and is seen as a ‘mental illness’. While the perspective of homosexuality in India during the pre - historic times was not so rigid and parochial as it is today. One of the main reasons as to why the Indian society views homosexuality as ‘unnatural’ and ‘sinful’ is due to the colonial influences where the British considered it against the Christian laws and values and hence led to the introduction of Section 377 of The Indian Penal Code in 1861, which criminalized homosexual acts framing them as ‘unnatural’ and shaped the society into a negative space.

Even after independence, homosexual men lived discreet and married women to escape the marital pressure they faced from their families and from society.

The 90’s

The 90’s was an era that is known for its Bollywood movies, dance, music and was seen as one of the most valuable and missed era by most of the millennials and Gen Z’s. There was a noticeable shift in the culture in lifestyle, intellectual thinking, culture, one of the main reasons for this shift was due to the then Indian Government turning itself into an Open Economy in 1991. This led to many western establishments opening their franchises in India. This initiative not only influenced western clothing styles on Indians but also made the society more liberal and broad minded.

Many Queer associations and organizations were formed to bring awareness and advocate for gay rights and provide help to the people belonging to the LGBTQ community.

While the social environment was not fully supportive of this, there was a remarkable change in the mindset of people, families started supporting their children, friends started supporting their friends and people started opening up about their queerness mindset and struggles with their friends and companions.

But, the Indian society was not fully inclusive of this idea, orthodox, hyper - religious and conservative individuals saw this as an opportunity to create new controversies and mark homosexuality as a 'mental illness' in humans and branding them as a 'menace' to the society and culture. Despite there being a shift in thinking among the people, men who identified themselves as 'gay' faced marital pressure to get married, these families used emotions as an excuse in order to convince these gay men to get married, while some gay men who chose to stay unmarried were deemed 'weak' and 'scared' to take up responsibilities and were discouraged and disowned from their own families. While the society always likes to criticize successful, talented and brave individuals some gay men chose their life over the society and moved on in life.

This period is just not seen as eye - opening era for gay men, but also the transgender individuals, lesbians and other allies and sexualities. It was just not gay men who raised their voices but also the fierce lesbian women too. The earliest known LGBTQ protest in India was by AIDS Bhedbhav Virodhi Andolan (ABVA) on August 11, 1992, in Delhi to protest police harassment of men accused of homosexual activity. This protest played a significant role in bringing out the harassment, ill treatment and disrespect that homosexual individuals faced in the society. This was followed by the first Pride Parade, called the 'Friendship Walk' held on July 2, 1999, in Kolkata, where 15 activists gathered to demand visibility and rights for the community under the outline of the criminalizing Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code.

In the Contemporary Era

In the contemporary era, the acceptance of homosexuality has increased, and the society which once was narrow has started to transcend into a more neo - liberalistic society. Protests and rallies by the queer community was seen when the Apex Court declined to legalize Same - Sex marriage in 2009 when the Delhi High Court declared Section 377 of the IPC as unconstitutional and decriminalized homosexuality, which

caused widespread dissatisfaction among the LGBTQ community. Formation of new organisations and associations have made homosexual individuals feel more included in society. With the rise of social media platforms, queer individuals have spoken about their own experiences of hate, violence and abuse faced by their families, colleagues or close friends which has impacted the present youth who are broad and liberal to think and support these individuals. Increase in queer parties such as Dude Party, Kitty Su, etc have successfully made queer individuals comfortable, especially gay men. A topic which was seen as a taboo is now spoken in public, mostly among young audiences to show that being 'gay' does not make an individual fragile or worthless. While homosexuality in the present generation is still seen as a controversy among people, the volume of hate received by people of the contemporary world has reduced to some extent, as the individuals who were discreet about their sexuality back in their days have shared their heart breaking experiences and the trauma they had to face back in their days. Stories of resilient gay men who were brave to face societal backlash became inspirations to the present generation queer youth to be brave hearted, strong, and proud of their identity. Recently on October 17, 2023, the Supreme Court rejected pleas to legalize same-sex marriage, holding that the right to marry is not a fundamental right and that it is up to the legislature to pass laws for this purpose. A five-judge bench delivered the verdict affirming that same-sex couples did not have a right to marry under existing law, such as the Special Marriage Act. But this did not make many activists and Queer organisations to lose hope, but to continue fighting for their rights.

One of the main factors as to why the present day youth are much more supportive of homosexuality is due to emphasis on intersectionality where teens debate on the existence of homosexuality in India not being a western influence nor a new concept but which has been a part of the society for many years. Influence of social media has tremendously changed the mindset of people particularly the cohort of the Digital Natives, millions of young adults use various social media platforms to express their thoughts and experiences, to educate and create a sense of belonging to the individuals who still are confused about their sexuality or in the closet. The introduction of queer safe bars and restaurants in the big cities in India has made gay men feel safe and enjoyable which once was a strict taboo.

Furthermore, the Parliament also passed new Queer relating laws like the Transgender Persons(Protection of Rights) Act in 2019 prohibits discrimination against transgender people in various sectors like education, employment, healthcare, and housing. It grants transgender individuals the right to be self-identified and obtain a transgender person

certificate from their respective government official to update their name on official documents.

Conclusion

In conclusion, homosexuality is not 'unnatural' or considered as a 'sin' but rather a concept that has been part of the Indian society. It's time that people change their outdated views on such matters relating to human sexuality and identities. The current political atmosphere being controlled by the far - right ideologies and principles which focus on social and cultural conservatism, it seems like a strenuous task to advocate justice and rights but nothing is impossible when hard work and support go hand in hand.

Ultimately, In today's India, where progress is celebrated in every sphere, the continued discrimination against homosexuality exposes a deep contradiction, for love between two people of the same gender is as natural and human as any other bond, and unless society learns to confront its prejudice with empathy, replace its silence with acceptance, and honor the dignity of all identities, the vision of an inclusive nation will remain incomplete, reminding us that true freedom can never exist without freedom to love.

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